

Toward an Interdisciplinary Cyberinfrastructure for Material Samples

What is iSamples?

iSamples is a 4 year, [NSF funded project](#) (established in August 2020), to build cyberinfrastructure that intends to revolutionize discoverability and the management of material samples. This includes:

1. Providing a single location for discovery of physical samples
2. Enabling previously impossible connections among samples
3. Supporting existing research efforts that collect and manage samples
4. Facilitating interdisciplinary collaborations using sample information
5. Providing an efficient solution for Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) samples

iSamples will enable these goals through the design, implementation, and deployment of technical components that include:

- An extensible core metadata model and associated controlled vocabularies for data concepts common across representative collections.
- iSamples-in-a-Box (iSB), a standalone software package for sample metadata storage and management, creating persistent identifiers for samples, and which will provide a translation service to and from the common model.
- iSamples-Central (iSC), a central discovery and persistent identifier resolution service which acts as a connection and integration hub for all iSB instances.

The creation of these components applies an iterative design process which includes gathering feedback from the initial use cases [GEOME](#), [Open Context](#), [SESAR](#), and the [Smithsonian Institution](#).

Accomplishments to Date

We published a 'marker' paper on the iSamples project in GigaScience: [Toward an interdisciplinary cyberinfrastructure for material samples](#). Presentations about iSamples can be found in our [Zenodo Community](#). In our work on the iSample components, we have:

- Developed prototype of [iSamples Central web interface](#).
- Completed a draft of the [core metadata model](#).
- Created upper level [controlled vocabularies for Specimen Type, Material Type, and Sampled Feature](#).

- Conducted several card sorting term mapping exercises to test the vocabularies against metadata from the 4 use cases.
- Evaluated machine learning approaches to facilitate the development of the middle layer controlled vocabularies to enhance sample descriptions for searching and browsing. for developing a 'sampled feature' controlled vocabulary.
- Mapped disparate records from the 4 use cases to the iSamples core model.
- Implemented iSamples in a Box service and deployed instances for each of the four use cases.
- Implemented iSamples Central content aggregation and indexing service and harvested, transformed, and indexed over 6 million physical sample records.
- Prototyped identifier minting (pending finalization of the DataCite infrastructure). Initial support is for IGSNs and DOIs, extending to ARKs.
- Containerized iSB and iSC services for ease of maintenance and deployment
- Implemented service metrics gathering

Plans for the Next Year

In the next year we will continue to evolve the iSB implementation to address requirements. The current implementation provides read-only synchronization of content from source collections. Further capabilities are to include support for physical sample record content creation with persistent, unique identifiers and user authentication via ORCID. We will also continue to seek feedback on design and implementation of the core infrastructure data models, services, and user interfaces.

Later this year we will be conducting a hackathon/workshop with select invitees to review and refine the core model and controlled vocabularies against their collections and community needs. If you are interested in taking part, please email sramdeen@ideo.columbia.edu.

How to Stay Engaged

You can stay updated on iSamples progress by following our [GitHub](#) account. We will also send a newsletter with updates to the community every 6 months (and as needed).

Feedback on iSamples models, vocabularies, and other products and developments is best provided by [submitting an issue on GitHub](#).

iSamples has a sister project, [Sampling Nature Research Coordination Network \(RCN\)](#). Sampling Nature aims to establish a network of stakeholders in the research community to enhance the natural history value chain for sustainability science.

The RCN is bringing together researchers from multiple disciplines through a series of workshops, working groups, and outreach activities, as well as a website and discussion forum. Attend their session at [SciDataCon 2022](#) or visit their website to learn how to join a Sampling Nature Working Group.